

Editorial

Dr Zhengang Guo: From the Man to the Medicine.

Dr Zhengang Guo, a pillar of Chinese Herbal Medicine, has left us an invaluable legacy. His career, defined by a passion for medicine and a relentless pursuit of effective and successful cures, has inspired generations of healthcare professionals. His special fondness for our country allowed many Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) practitioners in Portugal to learn from his methods and results. Born in China during a challenging historical period, Dr Guo developed a deep connection with the ancestral wisdom of traditional medicine. Following a family tradition of TCM specialists and herbalists, he masterfully combined these ancient practices with Western medical knowledge. After emigrating to the United States, he collaborated with prestigious universities with the ultimate goal of advancing Chinese herbal medicine and bridging the gap for Western doctors and scientists to whom it was largely unknown.

His professional journey was marked by a constant quest for excellence and innovation. Through tireless research and clinical practice, Dr Guo developed a holistic treatment method that addressed the person as a whole, considering not only physical symptoms but also emotional and spiritual well-being. This unique approach enabled him to help countless patients, many of whom faced conditions considered complex and challenging by conventional medicine—patients who had almost given up hope of reclaiming a healthy, active life.

Determined not to limit these results to his own clinic, he began sharing his discoveries early on. This led him to recover many family formulas, adapting them into formats suitable for the needs of his Western patients. The partnership with the International Institute of Alternative Medicine (IIMA) was fundamental in developing innovative phytotherapeutic formulas that became a benchmark in integrated medicine. These formulas, the result of years of research and clinical experience, demonstrate Dr Guo's commitment to providing safe and effective therapeutic solutions.

Throughout his life, Dr Guo developed hundreds of formulas tailored to the needs of his patients, particularly those suffering from pathologies prevalent in the Western lifestyle. He helped thousands of patients, many of whom became lifelong friends. Dr Guo's legacy transcends the boundaries of TCM, inspiring professionals across various healthcare fields to seek a more holistic and humanised approach to patient care. His vision of medicine centred on both the individual and nature continues to guide those who follow in his footsteps.

Dr Guo's absence is deeply felt by all who had the opportunity to know and work with him. His life was one of extreme dedication to healing and human well-being, particularly in the field of cancer, and his legacy will continue to inspire future generations.

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Academic and Scientific Summary

In this brief biographical record, we include further relevant details of his academic and scientific activity. His training in TCM began under the tutelage of his father, Guo Xiang-Li, who passed down a vast number of prescriptions and family technical treatments spanning six generations.

- 1970: Completed academic studies at Lanzhou Medical School, Lanzhou, Gansu, China.
- 1970–1975: Completed specialist studies at Linxia County Hospital, Gansu, in General Surgery, Gynaecology, Obstetrics, and Paediatrics, while deepening his knowledge of acupuncture and herbal medicine applied to these fields.

- 1975–1980: Practised at Lanzhou Chinese Medicine Hospital, where he furthered his expertise in these specialities. During this period, he completed his Ph.D. in Oncology.
- 1981–1983: Emigrated to the USA, where he held a post-doctoral fellowship at the Anderson Hospital & Tumor Institute, University of Houston, Texas.
- 1983–1985: Served as a Research Associate at the College of Pharmacy, University of Illinois Chicago.

During his professional and academic tenure in the USA, he obtained certifications as a Surgical Oncologist, as well as a Specialist in Acupuncture, Herbal Medicine, Nutrition, and TCM. He was a member of ASCO (American Society of Clinical Oncology) and AAOM (American Association of Oriental Medicine).

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